

Species 1: *H. melpomene*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.79; high PNT

NOT test

Species 2: *H. numata*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.7; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.261

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.46

D
p.value = 0.01996

Background 2->1

D
p.value = 0.00357

Background 1->2

D
p.value = 0.00259

Species 1: *H. melpomene*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.76; high PNT

NDT test

Species 2: *H. numata*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.73; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red= $S1 > S2$, Blue= $S1 < S2$, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.266

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.484$

D
p.value = 0.01796

Background 2→1

D
p.value = 0.00344

Background 1→2

D
p.value = 0.00257